

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF PREDIABETES AS PREVENTION OF TYPE 2 DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Prediabetes is defined as a disorder in which the criteria for diabetes mellitus are not met, but normal blood glucose values are exceeded; this intermediate hyperglycemia is associated with a high risk of developing diabetes and cardiovascular disease. The number of patients with diabetes mellitus continues to grow steadily, and therefore the role of timely interventions at the stage of prediabetes is obvious. A modern approach to preventing the progression of prediabetes includes correcting risk factors for cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, weight loss and/or prevention of weight gain, and improving the quality of life. The first-line therapy for prediabetes is lifestyle modification, which includes changes in diet, physical activity, weight management, bad habits, and sleep hygiene. Thus, a non-pharmacological approach to the treatment of patients, aimed at reducing excess weight, plays a major role. In conditions of insufficient effectiveness of measures to change lifestyle, it is advisable to prescribe drug therapy. Metformin is the first-line drug for preventing the progression of carbohydrate metabolism disorders. In addition to lifestyle modification, orlistat, drugs from the group of GLP-1 analogues, thiazolidinediones, and acarbose have also demonstrated their effectiveness. Bariatric surgery is associated with improved glycemic control in prediabetic patients.

Despite modern medical achievements, the incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) continues to grow steadily, and so do healthcare costs. This trend is observed not only in Russia, but also in other developed countries. In this regard, the healthcare sector faces an important medical and social task - preventing an increase in the number of patients. This task can be solved through prevention, diagnosis and treatment of patients with prediabetes. Prediabetes includes forms of carbohydrate metabolism disorders in which the criteria for manifest DM are not achieved, but normal blood glucose values are exceeded; such

intermediate hyperglycemia is associated with a high risk of developing diabetes and cardiovascular diseases (CVD) against the background of dyslipidemia. According to the International Diabetes Federation, the world population suffering from diabetes in 2021 was 537 million people, in addition, the number of people suffering from diabetes is expected to increase, which, according to preliminary data, will be 643 million by 2030, and 783 million by 2045. It is also worth noting that more than 90% of all cases of diabetes in the world are type 2 [1]. Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) in 2021 was registered in 541 million adults (10.6% of the adult population of the world), and impaired fasting glycemia (IFG) - in 319 million (6.2%). According to estimates of the International Diabetes Federation, in 2045 this number will increase to 730 million (11.4%) and 441 million (6.9%) people, respectively [1]. When analyzing the prevalence of type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes in the Russian Federation in dynamics for the period 2016–2020, one can note an increase in the prevalence of diabetes, mainly due to type 2 diabetes. Since 2016, there has been an increase of more than 300 thousand new patients with diabetes. In total, according to the online diabetes registry, which includes 84 regions and 4,658 medical and preventive institutions, as of 01.01.2021, the total number of patients with diabetes registered with dispensaries was 4,799,552 (3.23% of the population of the Russian Federation), of which 5.5% (265.4 thousand) had type 1 diabetes, 92.5% (4.43 million) had type 2 diabetes, 2.0% (99.3 thousand) had other types of diabetes, of which 67.3 thousand were IGT, and 12.1 thousand were NGT [2]. The incidence of type 2 diabetes 5 years after the diagnosis of IGT or NGT is estimated at 26 and 50%, respectively [1]. The term prediabetes includes IGT and IFG, as well as a combination of IGT and IFG, since patients with these conditions have a high risk of developing diabetes [3]. IFG was added to IGT in the American Diabetes Association (ADA) definitions of prediabetes in 1997, since repeated observations show little agreement between them [4].

The development of IGT and IFG occurs as a result of a number of specific pathophysiological processes. Although prediabetes is based on insulin resistance, mainly in individuals with excess body weight and obesity, a number of studies have demonstrated differences in the main disorders underlying IFG from the pathophysiological changes underlying IGT. Taken together, the results demonstrated signs of beta-cell dysfunction and insulin resistance in IGT and IFG, which differ slightly from each other [4]. Individuals with isolated IFG predominantly have hepatic insulin resistance with normal muscle sensitivity, reduced hepatic glucose utilization, and the ability to suppress gluconeogenesis. In addition, IFG is characterized by beta-cell dysfunction, a decrease in phase I insulin secretion, which is manifested by elevated fasting glucose with normal postprandial hypoglycemia [5]. IGT is predominantly characterized by skeletal muscle resistance with reduced glucose utilization and is also accompanied by beta-cell dysfunction [5]. IGT is characterized by a defect in the late phase of insulin secretion with predominant hyperglycemia in response to an oral or intravenous glucose load. Individuals with combined IFG and IGT have both hepatic and muscle insulin resistance. Thus, individuals with prediabetes who have either IFG, IGT, or both have different patterns of insulin resistance and beta-cell dysfunction. The aim of the study by L. Perreault et al. [4] was to determine whether the combination of IGT and IFG (IGT/IGN) represents a third pathway (in addition to isolated IGT and IGT) or a final common pathway to diabetes, and showed that the absolute differences between the groups were small

but significant. Taken together, the results indicate that IGT/IGN may be a distinct prediabetic syndrome [4]. It is likely that in patients with IGT/IGN, insulin resistance of both the liver and muscle tissue, as well as beta-cell dysfunction, play a role in the pathogenesis of hyperglycemia [6]. Detection of IGT/IGN defects has practical clinical significance, since the risk of progression to overt diabetes is 3 times higher than with isolated IGT or IGN. Risk factors Traditional risk factors for prediabetes are obesity, arterial hypertension (AH), age 45 years and older, gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), aggravated family history of diabetes mellitus, and low physical activity. Analyzing the results of the Russian NATION study, we can conclude that the determining risk factors for prediabetes are age 45 years and older, obesity, and AH. Moreover, among patients with grade 3 obesity, prediabetes was detected more often (39.7%) than in patients with grade 2 (37.8%) and grade 1 (30.3%). A combination of factors in one patient is equivalent to a higher risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus [7]. The study also examined the effect of GDM as a risk factor. The questionnaire results showed that women diagnosed with GDM were approximately twice as likely to develop type 2 diabetes, but the prevalence of prediabetes did not differ significantly between those with a history of GDM and those without. The study also examined risk factors such as low physical activity and low consumption of fruits and vegetables. The authors report that low physical activity and low consumption of these products played a role in the study.

the least role in the development of diabetes. The authors attribute this to the insufficient objectivity of the respondents' assessment of physical activity and the fact that respondents did not provide accurate information on the quantitative assessment of their consumption of vegetables and fruits [8]. The authors also note that a healthy lifestyle plays a significant role and reduces the risk of developing type 2 diabetes by 75%. At the individual level, patients are recommended to maintain optimal body weight, avoid smoking and alcohol abuse, follow a healthy diet and increase their level of physical activity [8]. According to the PREDAPS study, it was demonstrated that obesity, low levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol and hypertension are modifiable risk factors independently associated with the presence of prediabetes in both sexes. The magnitudes of the associations were stronger for men than for women. Abdominal obesity in both men and women showed the strongest association with prediabetes. Exogenous-constitutional obesity is also associated with prediabetes in men, although statistical significance disappeared after adjustment for all factors [9].

Diagnostics Prediabetes is a cardiometabolic condition with various manifestations of intermediate carbohydrate metabolism disorder – IGT, NGT, NGT/IGT. Prediabetes diagnostics are based on the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT). The test is performed in the morning on an empty stomach 8–12 hours after the last meal. 2–3 days before the test, the patient should consume a sufficient amount of carbohydrates with food and have a standard physical activity for his lifestyle. Different organizations define prediabetes using criteria that do not always coincide (Table 1). The World Health Organization (WHO) has defined prediabetes as a state of intermediate hyperglycemia using two or a combination of criteria based on the OGTT [10]: 1. Fasting plasma glucose level – 6.1–6.9 mmol/l, determining the NGN. 2. Plasma glucose level after 2 hours during OGTT – 7.8–11.0 mmol/l, determining NTG. The ADA, in turn, uses 3 criteria for diagnosing prediabetes [11]: 1. Fasting plasma glucose – 5.6–6.9 mmol/l, has a lower threshold value compared to WHO criteria. 2. The glucose level after 2 hours during OGTT is 7.8–11.0 mmol/l, which is

similar to the WHO threshold value. 3. Glycated hemoglobin level (HbA1c) – 5.7–6.4%, which is an additional criterion for determining prediabetes. These values may indicate chronic hyperglycemia and the presence of prediabetes, but OGTT should be used to confirm the diagnosis [12]. The Russian Association of Endocrinologists (RAE) evaluates any of the early disturbances of carbohydrate metabolism during OGTT as a criterion for prediabetes [3]: 1. NGN, defined as a fasting plasma glucose level of 6.1–6.9 mmol/l, with a normal glucose level after 2 hours of OGTT. 2. IGT, defined as a 2-hour plasma glucose level of 7.8–11.1 mmol/L after ingestion of 75 g glucose during an OGTT, with normal fasting glucose levels. The additional ADA criterion does not coincide with the recommendations of the WHO and the RAE, which define an intermediate HbA1c level of 6.0–6.4%, which in itself does not allow a diagnosis to be made, but suggests the presence of a risk of diabetes and the conduct of additional studies [3]. These discrepancies can be explained by the results of studies showed a poor correlation between the HbA1c level and IFN or IGT [13–15]. Although it is believed that HbA1c reflects the average blood glucose level and should ideally more accurately reflect hyperglycemia, this is not the case in all situations. The HbA1c level can be determined to a certain extent by genetic factors that are independent of blood glucose levels, concomitant diseases, including those accompanied by hemoglobinopathy, and therefore may be an inaccurate tool for measuring the average blood glucose level [16, 17]. However, HbA1c is also considered a more convenient screening method that does not require fasting blood donation [18]. Based on the available data, it appears that prediabetes, as defined by the various alternative criteria, consists of an overlapping group of individuals with one or more abnormalities in glucose fluctuations. It is possible that the presence of IGT and IGT identifies individuals with different abnormalities in their glucose metabolism, and the presence of both conditions indicates a more pronounced disturbance of overall glucose homeostasis.

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